

ONLINE SHOPPING: A CHANGING SCENARIO IN INDIA

Mr. Nitin Ghevar Chaudhari

Asst. Professor,

KCE Society's M.J. College, (Autonomous), Jalgaon

Abstract:

Online shopping plays a very important role in the 21st century. Most people prefer to buy online products and services instead of physically buying them. Nowadays most people have less time and have the busiest schedule therefore people prefer online shopping. 4G Internet availability, smartphones, and new online shopping platforms changed the Indian perspective of shopping. There are some challenges before online shopping platforms in India such as losses due to return policy, problems regarding selling perishable goods, after-sale service, problems related to shipping products in remote areas, etc. Opportunities before online shopping platforms are changing customer buying behaviour towards online shopping, new technology, increasing transportation services and infrastructural facilities in rural areas, etc.

Offline shopping platforms play important role in rural areas as well as for those who are not familiar with the technology. In offline shopping customers can get good after-sale service, surety about the reliability of the product can physically handle the product before buying, well dealing with uneducated people these are some points where offline shopping modes beat online shopping platforms. Some products and services where online shopping is not more preferable e.g. Hospital related services, cloth shopping, etc. But still, online shopping is capturing more market share in India of shopping in this decade. In this paper, various aspects of changing online scenarios in India are studied.

Keywords: *Online shopping, online shopping platform, Customer buying behaviour, product & services*

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/amierj/>

Introduction:

Online shopping is the activity of buying a product over the internet using an online platform. In online shopping, customers visit the seller’s website or apps online, choose the product whatever they want, fill in their contact details, the delivery address where they want to receive it, and place the order. Payment of online shopping can be done online at the time of placing the order or customers can pay at the time of receiving the product. Customers can buy various goods and services online mode. The main online shopping platforms in India are Flipkart, Amazon, Myntra, Ajo, Snapdeal, Book My Show, Pharmeasy, BigBasket, Nykaa, TATA CLiQ, Paytm Mall, Swiggy, MakeMyTrip, Goibibo, Zomato, 1mg, etc.

Research Methodology:

1. Primary Data: Primary data are used for this study. It includes interviews.
2. Secondary Data: Secondary data includes internet, Shopping apps, articles etc.

Hypothesis:

1. H1- Online shopping platform has taken a higher market share in India in recent year.
2. H1 - Online shopping has challenges & opportunities.

Objectives:

1. To study the opportunities and challenges of online shopping platforms in India.
2. To study various aspects of changing online shopping scenarios in India
3. To study the trend of increase in online shopping in India

E Commerce Market Turnover trend in India in recent years.

As per reports published by Statista, India's E-Commerce Market turnover in India in 2014 was \$14 billion US dollars and It shows increasing trends in recent years. Even in 2020 in the Covid19 pandemic, E-commerce market turnover reached \$50 billion US dollars and India became the eighth largest E-Commerce market in the world. According to NASSCOM, Indian E-Commerce Market is expected to reach \$56.6 billion US dollars in 2021. This number is expected to reach \$200 billion US dollars by 2027

Why have most Indian preferred online shopping over offline in recent years?

✓ Convenience

Many times, people do not have time to go store shopping. Online shopping can be done using mobile apps, internet from our home. Customers receive the product at their home called home delivery. variety of products can be select, shopping site provides cash on delivery, online payment, credit facilities options these things are convenient to the customers.

✓ Availability of Internet

Smartphones and 3G,4G technology have boosted the usage of the internet in India in recent years. There are 622 million Internet users in India in the year 2020 and it is expected to reach 900 million in 2025.

✓ E-Commerce Market strategies

Established E-Commerce sites offer attractive discounts & offer on online shopping. e.g. Flipcart offers a large discount in the 'Big Billions Days' sale, Amazon offers the same in the 'Great Indian Festival' sale.

In 'Flipcart big billion Days' 8 days sale of 2021, Customers saved Rs. 11500 crores. Over 3.75 lakh sellers had joined this sale and 55% growth in the sellers compared to

sales in the year 2020. Same strategies used by other shopping platforms. These figures can show the effectiveness of marketing strategies.

✓ Changing consumer behaviour

Consumer behaviour is changing in recent years regarding online shopping. Most online shopping sites provide goods with huge discounts, free delivery, and various offers. B2B transactions eliminate the cost of intermediary and that's the wise cost is less compared

to offline in-store shopping. In India customers are price-centric therefore such discounts, offers attract the consumers.

During the covid19 pandemic due to restrictions in the offline store, online shopping is preferably chosen by the customers.

Challenges before online shopping in India:

- ✓ Cash on delivery problems

Many Indian customers still do not reply on online payment. They prefer the 'cash on delivery option. Cash on delivery option is perilous and laborious.

- ✓ Slow Internet Connectivity

In India, still, internet connectivity is slow in many village areas. This creates problems for online shopping growth. However, this issue can be lesser in upcoming years

- ✓ Return Policies

Many Indians return the product after buying online. Still, there are many new customers on the online shopping site and they sometimes just try to purchase online and return it. Return policy expensive for eCommerce retailers. They suffer a loss due to the return policy.

- ✓ Supply Chain Issues in rural areas

In India still, infrastructure facilities are underdeveloped as compared to western countries US, UK, etc. Therefore, online product delivery within time becomes difficult. In cities there are such facilities are available but in rural areas such facilities are underdeveloped. As per the reports published by Statista, In India, almost 65% population lives in rural areas but due to insufficient infrastructure facilities, the supply chain is not easily available in rural areas therefore online shopping is not deliverable in rural areas Since the rural population is higher compared to urban, E-Commerce business miss this higher market of rural areas.

✓ Logistics-related problems:

Sometimes products are damaged while in transit or lost. If customers select a fast delivery option then they need to pay extra charges, sometimes customers receive the wrong product or customers return the wrong product. These are all the challenges before online shopping

New Opportunities for the E-Commerce business in upcoming years

1. Scope in Rural market

In India, almost 65% population live in rural areas where online shopping services are not easily available due to supply chain issues. In the future, if efficient supply chains are available in rural areas, E-commerce businesses will grow in rural areas in upcoming years. In rural areas, agricultural tools, seeds, fertilizers, pesticides have high demand. Domestic goods demand also there in the rural market. In India, internet facilities are available all over the country, and a new generation is educated and accepting new modes of shopping.

2. Ecommerce delivery drones

Drones mean flying robots' machines that can be controlled manually or automatically. Now a day's main problem relating to online shopping is delivery time. If the goods are perishable then fast delivery is required. E.g. food or vegetable order this problem will be reduced. In the future flying robots will deliver the product to the customers and robots will deliver the product faster. E.g. Amazon prime air granted a patent for its ground-based mobile drone fulfilment and maintenance carriers in 2017.

3. Social media shopping

Social Media usage is high in India. E.g. WhatsApp 487.5 Million, Facebook 340 million, Instagram 180 million, Twitter 22.1 million as per Statista report in July 2021. Companies know well the importance of social media therefore many companies are shifted their online marketing towards social media to reach a maximum number of customers. Many people are buying online products by using the links on social media. In the future investment in social media marketing will grow the E-Commerce business faster.

4. Personalize experience

Customers prefer some products to purchase offline by taking personalize the experience. In offline shopping, customers can physically visit, see the product and clear all doubts relating to the product which he wants to purchase. E-Commerce sites do not have such a facility but E-Commerce sites are working on it. In the future E-Commerce site will

give personalized experiences to their customers so that people will purchase the product after taking personalize the experience.

Conclusion:

Online shopping captures the large market in India. It is convenient to the customers and due to availability of internet facilities and smartphone it growing up. Effective marketing strategies of online sites changed consumers' behaviour towards online shopping positively. India's E-Commerce Market turnover in India in 2014 was \$14 billion US dollars, in 2020 was \$50 billion US dollars and expected to reach \$200 billion US dollars by 2027

There are challenges before online shopping sites includes cash on delivery problems, slow internet connectivity issues, return policies, unavailability of the supply chain in rural areas, etc. but these issues can be solved in upcoming years. About 60% population lives in rural areas in India, there is an opportunity in the rural market If a good supply chain is available in rural areas in the future, the rural market will be easily captured by E-Commerce businesses. In the future Delivery by drone drones make orders faster. Providing personalized experience, using Social media shopping strategy Ecommerce business will grow faster in upcoming years.

Bibliography:

1. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/792047/india-e-commerce-market-size/>
2. <https://www.ibef.org/industry/ecommerce.aspx>
3. <https://www.Flipcart.com>
4. <https://www.amazon.in>
5. <https://www.perceptionssystem.com/blog/5-major-challenges-faced-ecommerce-businesses-india/>
6. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1012239/india-population-by-region/>
7. <https://www.practicalecommerce.com/8-commercial-drone-delivery-companies>